

Diversity and Distribution of Ants (*Hymenoptera: Formicidae*) in the Northern Area of Pakistan

Rahat Siraj¹, Izhar Ullah^{2*}, Mohammad Yousaf^{2**}, Shumaila Noreen², Said Nawaz Khan², Rimsha Khan³ and Syed Sabir Hussain Shah²

1. Department of Zoology, Hazara University Sub Campus Battagram, Pakistan
2. Department of Zoology, Hazara University Mansehra Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan
3. Department of Zoology, Lahore College for Women University

*Corresponding author e-mail: izharullahizhar666@gmail.com;
muhammadyousaf33bjr@gmail.com

SUMMARY

The present preliminary study was conducted from March 2024 to June 2024 to evaluate the diversity and distribution of ants in District Battagram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Ants were collected across a variety of habitats using various techniques, including pit traps, hand collection, protein or sugar bait, and buccal aspirators. Twelve different species of ants were revealed, classified into two subfamilies and seven genera. The subfamilies Formicinae and Myrmicinae are both members of the family Formicidae. Myrmicinae was determined to be the dominant subfamily, followed by Formicinae. The subfamily Myrmicinae is represented by five genera, including *Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, *Monomorium*, and *Pheidole*, while Formicinae includes two genera, *Camponotus* and *Formica*. In terms of genera distribution, *Camponotus* is recorded as diverse, having five species. *Monomorium* has two species, and the remaining genera, namely *Formica*, *Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, and *Pheidole*, are each represented by a single species. Species belonging to the *Camponotus* genus mentioned in the present exploration include *C. copressus*, *C. castaneus*, *C. consobrinus*, *C. sericeus*, and *C. vagus*. *Monomorium* was recorded with two species: *M. minimum* and *M. indicum*, while the genera with single species were *Crematogaster walshi*, *Formica fusca*, *Messor barbarus*, *Meranoplus bicolor*, and *Pheidole indica himalaya*. The Shannon-Wiener diversity index (H') value is approximately ($H = 2.36$), which is <2.5 , indicating that the ants have moderate diversity in District Battagram.

Keywords: Diversity, Distribution, Ants, Hymenoptera, Formicidae, Battagram

INTRODUCTION

The most recognizable and varied collection of invertebrates on the planet is the ants. This can be attributed to their widespread and typically evident nature as a group. They are eusocial and can be found in a wide range of soil ecosystems, such as horizontal rainforest swamps, arid regions, seacoastlines, high elevations, and deep below ground to the tops of the tallest trees (Bolton, 1994). However, they are totally absent in some areas, such as Greenland, Antarctica, the island of Iceland, and some territories (Holldobler and Wilson, 1990), none of which have any native ant species (Wilson and Taylor, 1967). Ants are a widespread, well-known, and prevalent category of insects that belong to the family *Formicidae*, superfamily *Vespoidea*, and order *Hymenoptera* of the class *Insecta*. They are considered essential species

worldwide, accounting for thirty percent of the land environment's faunal biomass. Over time, they have evolved into a more diverse and ecologically rich group among insect societies (Majer, 1985). With 296 genera, 16 subfamilies, and approximately 15,000 species, the family *Formicidae* is home to over 15,000 ants worldwide (Bolton, 1994). Of these, over 12,000 species have been described (Bolton et al., 2006), and many more are still undiscovered (Holldobler and Wilson, 1990). Given their social nature, ants guard their territory together, making them highly social insects. In case of an assault on their colony, they employ specific weaponry including shots, chewing, and chemical sprays like formic acid (Clarke, 1985). The army ant species is utilized in South Africa and throughout Africa for surgical procedures (Gottrup and Leaper, 2004). The species of foraging ants are capable of traveling up to 700 feet from their nest site. The worker ants are used in various areas as food, biological control agents, and for medicinal purposes. There are two types of weaver ants. The first is called *Oecophylla smaragdina*, and it is found in Asia and Australia. The second is an African species called *Oecophylla longinoda* (Wetterer, 2017). A survey was conducted to investigate the ant fauna (*Hymenoptera*) in the district of Swabi in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, taking into account all of these details. This project will produce some data regarding the distribution and richness of ants until further research on ants is conducted in this field.

The ant fauna of Pakistan is poorly understood. For instance, Haji (2008) reported 11 species under seven genera of house ants from Karachi; Umair et al. (2012) reported 21 species under 13 genera of three subfamilies from the Potohar Plateau; Ahmed et al. (2013) reported seven species from Quetta, Balochistan; Bodlah et al. (2016) reported two *Tetraponera* species—*T. allaborans* and *T. nigra*—for the first time from Pakistan, recorded from Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Recently, Usman et al. (2017) reported 17 species under 12 genera of the subfamilies Myrmicinae and Camponotinae from the district of Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Pakistan is located in a transitional zone between the Palearctic and Oriental regions, with a smaller degree of influence from the Afrotropical region. This leads to a highly diversified fauna. Taxonomic research on Pakistani ants has been severely neglected, despite the country's significant biogeographic location. This research was designed to investigate the ant species in the district of Battagram, taking into consideration the significance of ants for the region. Within the superfamily Vespoidea of the order *Hymenoptera*, the family *Formicidae* is where ants are classified taxonomically. By use of a link that connects the mesosoma with the gaster, geniculate antennae, and the consistently present metapleural gland in ants, they are distinguished from the other components of the order (Wilson, 1971). This region may have one or two segments. There are currently over 15,000 kinds of ants worldwide (Bolton, 1994), of which more than 12,000 have been described (Bolton et al., 2006; Ullah and W. Khan, 2024). The family *Formicidae* has 16 subfamilies and 296 genera. Even though many are still awaiting clarification, there are still a lot of unidentified species (Holober and Wilson, 1990). Four of the extinct subfamilies' fourteen ancient genera and sixty-one of the surviving subfamilies' lost genera were identified from fossil data of ants (Bolton & Bolton, 1995). The current study was the first conducted to explore the previously undiscovered ant fauna in the district of Battagram and to find the distribution of ant species in different localities of the district.

METHODS AND MATERIAL

Study area

The most recent study was conducted in District Battagram, which spans 1,301 square kilometers and is located in the western region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, between 34°33' and 34°47' N and 72°54' and 73°15' E. Its lush green mountains range in altitude from 525 m at Thakot to over 4,690 m at Sukaisar (Ullah et al., 2024; Shah et al., 2023). The region's climate is variable, ranging from subtropical to "alpine" conditions. Battagram has a variety of agricultural lands, wasteland, forests, and grassy fields; most people rely on cultivation, which is followed by animal husbandry (Haq et al., 2010). The majority of inhabitants earn a living through food production, followed by animal husbandry. They grow wheat, corn, rice, soybeans, and greens (Muhammad 2004; Ullah et al., 2024).

Collection of specimens

The sample was collected from different localities of District Battagram, including Chappargram, Pagora, Tamai, Battagram, Ajmera, Kuzabanda, Bilankot, Hotal Deshan, Kakar Shang, Shumlai, Thakot, Allai Pashto, Kandao, and Kasai Road. Perform research in areas that are ideal for ant populations. Look closely and find ants in a variety of tiny habitats, including the soil, plants, leaves, and beneath stumps and stones. To successfully capture ants while causing the least amount of damage to the surroundings, use specific gathering techniques. Take caution when handling gathered ants to prevent hurting or upsetting them. Handle ants slowly using soft tools, aspirators, or tweezers. To prevent spreading fats or pollutants, try not to handle ants with just your fingertips.

Preservation

After the gathering procedure, cyanide-filled bottles were used to kill the selected ants. An Eppendorf tube filled with 90% ethanol was utilized to preserve the collected ant data. The diary recorded each specimen's location, temperature, ecosystem, latitude, coordinates, and tube code, in addition to the collection date, time, and place. The ethanol in the tubes was changed every few days to prevent sample deterioration. During this preservation technique, the ants' physical traits and attributes are maintained while they are transferred and stored for further research.

Identification

Traditional scientific writings, readily available codes, and comparative photos were utilized for the determination process. The specimens have been recognized utilizing the readily accessible taxonomic codes down to the kind stage.

RESULT

Since there hasn't been enough research done on Pakistan's ant fauna, the primary objective of the current study was to identify the many kinds and varieties of ant species in District Battagram. Using techniques and methods like sugar bait or protein bait, pitfall traps, simple hand collection, and buccal aspirators, the ant specimens were collected from the varied ecosystems in 12 different locales within District

Battagram. Twelve ant species in all were identified through the identification keys of the gathered specimens. These species were divided into two subfamilies and seven genera: the families *Formicidae* include both *Formicinae* and *Myrmicinae*. *Myrmicinae* was determined to be the predominant subfamily, next to *Formicinae*. Five genera—*Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, *Monomorium*, and *Phidole*—represented the *Myrmicinae* subfamily. However, the *Formicidae* family also contains the genera *Formica* and *Camponotus*. With five species, the genus *Camponotus* was found to be among the broadest if its distribution was examined at the genus stage.

There are two species in *Monomorium*, while there is only one species in each of the other genera: *Formica*, *Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, and *Phiedole*. The *Camponotus* genus includes species such as *C. copressus*, *C. castaneus*, *C. consobrinus*, *C. sericeus*, and *C. vagus* that are described in the current study. The two species *M. minimum* and *M. indicum* reported *Monomorium*. However, the genera *Crematogaste walshi*, *Formica fusca*, *Messor barbarus*, and *Meranoplus* only have one kind each the families *Formicidae* includes both *Formicinae* and *Myrmicinae*. *Myrmicinae* was determined to be the predominant subfamily across such, next to *Formicidae*. Five genera; —*Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, *Monomorium*, and *Phiedole*; —represented the *Myrmicinae* subfamily. However, the *Formicidae* family also contains the genera *Formica* and *Camponotus*. With five species, the genus *Camponotus* was found to be among the broadest if its distribution was examined at the genera stage. There are two members in *Monomorium*, while there is only one species in each of the other genera: *Formica*, *Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, and *Phiedole*. The *Camponotus* genus includes species such as *C. copressus*, *C. castaneus*, *C. consobrinus*, *C. sericeus*, and *C. vagus* which are described in the current study. The two species *M. minimum* and *M. indicum* reported *Monomorium*. However, the genera *Crematogaste walshi*, *Formica fusca*, *Messor barbarus*, *Metanolopus bicolor*, and *Meranoplus* only have one kind each (Table 1).

Table 1: Systematic position of Ant species collected from District Battagram

Sub family	Genus	Species
Formicinae	<i>Camponotus</i>	<i>Camponotus compressus</i>
		<i>Camponotus vagus</i>
		<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i>
		<i>Camponotus castaneus</i>
		<i>Camponotus sericeus</i>
	<i>Formica</i>	<i>Formica fusca</i>
	<i>Crematogaster</i>	<i>Crematogaster walshi</i>
Myrmicinae	<i>Messor</i>	<i>Messor barbarus</i>
	<i>Meranoplus</i>	<i>Meranoplus bicolor</i>
	<i>Monomorium</i>	<i>Monomorium minimum</i>
		<i>Monomorium indicum</i>
	<i>Phiedole</i>	<i>Phiedole indica himalyana</i>

Table 2: Locality-wise Distribution of Ants species in District Battagram

Species	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12	L13	L14
<i>Camponotus vagus</i>		+				+	+			+		+		+
<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i>	+		+											
<i>Camponotus castaneus</i>							+	+						
<i>Camponotus sericeus</i>		+								+		+	+	
<i>Camponotus compressus</i>	+	+					+					+		
<i>Crematogaster walshi</i>	+		+			+					+			+
<i>Formica fusca</i>				+	+									
<i>Messor barbarus</i>	+	+	+	+		+	+		+	+	+			+
<i>Meranoplus bicolor</i>	+		+			+		+	+			+	+	
<i>Monomorium minimum</i>		+						+				+	+	
<i>Monomorium indicum</i>	+					+				+		+		
<i>Pheidole indica himalyana</i>	+		+			+	+	+	+	+				+

L1= Chappargram, L2= Pagora, L3= Tamai, L4= Battagram, L5= Ajmera, L6= Kuzabanda, L7= Kakar shang, L8= Shumlai, L9= Hotal deshan, L10= Thakot, L11= Bilankot, L12= Allai Pashto, L13= Kandao, L14= Kasai road.

Table 3: Ant species found in Different Habitats of the study area i.e. District Battagram

Species	H 1	H 2	H 3	H 4	H 5	H 6	H 7	H 8
<i>Camponotus vagus</i>			+		+			
<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i>								+
<i>Camponotus castaneus</i>	+	+						
<i>Camponotus sericeus</i>	+	+						
<i>Camponotus compressus</i>	+	+					+	
<i>Crematogaster walshi</i>	+							+
<i>Formica fusca</i>		+						+
<i>Messor barbarus</i>					+	+		
<i>Meranoplus bicolor</i>			+		+			
<i>Monomorium minimum</i>					+	+		

Monomorium indicum + + +

Pheidole indica himalyana + + +

H1=Agriculture, H2=Stony area, H3=Ground, H4=Home, H5= Grassy fields, H6= Trees, H7=Building, and H8= Bare ground.

Figure 1: Showing the Abundance of Families of Ants recorded from District Battagram

Statistical Analysis of Data

The data obtained during the current study were analyzed to find diversity index value, abundance, and species richness. To calculate the Shannon-Wiener diversity, the following formula was used.

$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^s p_i \ln p_i \qquad P_i = \frac{n_i}{N} \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Description:

H = Shannon-Wiener diversity index

S = Species

Pi = Percentage

Ln = Natural logarithm

ni = Number of individuals' species

N = Number of individuals of all types to determine species diversity

The Shannon-Wiener diversity index (H') ranges from 1.5 to 3.5, given in Table 4.

Table: 4 Range of Shannon wiener diversity index (H') value.

Index value	Category
<1.5	low diversity
1.5<x<2.5	Medium diversity
>2.5	high diversity

By applying the Shannon-Wiener diversity index, the find (H') value is round about (H = 2.36) given in table (4) which is <2.5, which indicates that the Ants have

medium diversity in District Battagram. The diversity index is a mathematical representation; it makes it easier to analyze the number of individual species and how much the diversity of species in the study area. When the Shannon index increases as both the evenness and richness of the community increase and vice versa.

Table 5: Shannon wiener diversity index (H') of Ants in the study area.

Name of Species	No of species	Pi	ln Pi	Pi*lnpi	H'
<i>Camponotus vagus</i>	31	0.107	-2.236	-0.239	2.36
<i>Camponotus consobrinus</i>	13	0.045	-3.105	-0.139	
<i>Camponotus castaneus</i>	20	0.069	-2.674	-0.184	
<i>Camponotus sericeus</i>	32	0.11	-2.204	-0.243	
<i>Camponotus compressus</i>	41	0.141	-1.956	-0.277	
<i>Crematogaster walshi</i>	19	0.066	-2.725	-0.179	
<i>Formica fusca</i>	4	0.014	-4.284	-0.059	
<i>Messor barbarus</i>	48	0.166	-1.799	-0.298	
<i>Meranoplus bicolor</i>	15	0.052	-2.962	-0.153	
<i>Monomorium minimum</i>	27	0.093	-2.374	-0.221	
<i>Monomorium indicum</i>	19	0.066	-2.725	-0.179	
<i>Pheidole indica himalyana</i>	21	0.072	-2.625	-0.19	
Total	290			-2.361	

Other diversity indexes were also found by applying Past software; all the indexes show that District Battagram has medium diversity of ants, while evenness (Evenness $e^{H/S}=0.8832$) indicates the species distribution is mostly uniform, as given in table 6).

Table 6: Show the different diversity indexes of Ants in the study area.

Indexes	District Battagram
Taxa_S	12
Individuals	290
Dominance_D	0.1031
Simpson_1-D	0.8969
Shannon_H	2.361
Evenness_ $e^{H/S}$	0.8832

Genus: *Camponotus*

Species: *Camponotus vagus* (Scopoli, 1763)

Character

The ant has dark-colored feet and is a black carpentry ant. The length limit for employees is 7–13 mm (0.28–0.51 in).

Habitat: The species were collected from the grassy fields and ground (Figure 2).

Genus: *Phiedole*

Species: *Phiedole himalayana* (Forel, 1902)

Character

Phiedole himalayana Length 2 mm; skull clear; pairs propodeal spikes wider than propodeal spiracle size; light brown color; posterior (earlobe) edge lightly indented the centre

Habitat: The species were collected from the grassy fields, bare ground and rooms.

Genus: *Camponotus*

Species: *Camponotus sericeus* (Fabricius, 1798)

Character: *Camponotus sericeus* is type of monogamous ants that can have colonies that up to 5000 workers. Their rate of growth is mediocre. The dimensions for a royal are 13–15 mm, employees range from 5-8 mm, and majors are 8–11 mm. Their skull is little red, while they feature abundant blonde locks on their belly, giving them a grayish appearance.

Habitat: The species were collected from the vegetation fields, grassy fields and stony area.

Genus: *Messor*

Species: *Messor barbarus* (Linnaeus, 1767)

Character

Often completely black and have a shiny coat and little white bristles all over their entire frame. The ants, like similar Messors, extract the grains and use their powerful teeth to crack open their shells, turning them into "ant-bread," an abundant protein source. It's the source of 90% of all nutrition these ants consume. They construct their nests beneath bushes as rocks in the elements. These construct spectacular homes up to 4 meters below the surface just for little ants.

Habitat: Specimens collected from streets and grassy fields.

Genus: *Camponotus*

Species: *Camponatus castaneus* (Latreille, 1802)

Character

Most of the time at night. The homes were discovered by MacGown and Brown (2006) in a leakage location in the soil at the base of *Fagus grandifolia*. *C. castaneus* typically inhabits somewhat warmed caves in tropical settings.

Habitat: Specimens collected from the stony and vegetation fields.

Genus: *Camponotus*

Character

Camponotus consobrinus, most prevalent names are Sugar Ant, Nocturnal Sugar Ant, and Joined Honey Ant, and who are indigenous to Australia. Their love of sweets and delicious meals earned them their popular names. An ant that stands out due to its brownish-orange belt surroundings his gaster

Habitat: Specimens collected from the bare ground.

Genus: *Monomorium*

Species: *Monomorium minutum* (Mayr, 1855)

Character

Monomorium minutum the males are roughly 1 to 2 mm long, and their queens are 4 to 5 mm long, with a glossy black color. This variety was identical, having a single employee tribe, and polygyne, which allows many queens to live in a nest. Typically, a colony has only a few thousand workers and is of average size.

Habitat: Specimens collected from trees and grassy fields.

Genus: *Monomorium*.

Species: *Monomorium indicum* (Forel, 1902)

Character

Antennal segment count on the *Monomorium indicum* is 10; 11; 12. Antennal ball density is progressive, 3, 4, Total number of teeth: 3-5 (2 in certain inquiries), 11–100 eyelids in the optic nerve Scrobes: nonexistent, There are no pronotal, mesonotal, or propodeal spines present. Lack of petiolar ridges Caste: intercastes in at least one species, polymorphism in some species, monomorphism Sting: in the moment, Abundant for Metaplural Gland, missing for Dune.

Habitat: Specimens were collected from the trees, grassy fields and kitchen.

Genus: *Crematogaster*

Species: *Crematogaster walshi* (Forel, 1902)

Character

The Saint Valentine ant is one of the common names for *Crematogaster walshi*, which are distinguished by a characteristic heart-like gaster (abdomen). Their limbs and torso are somewhat brown. Although this species' species have a propensity of lifting their upper bodies as warning they are often referred to as cocktail ants. An trees species is one that lives in trees at times acrobat ants are the name given to these ants.

Habitat: Species collected from the vegetation fields and bare ground.

Genus: *Meranoplus*

Species: *Meranolopus bicolor* (Guerin-Meneville, 1844)

Character

Meranolopus bicolor monogamous ant kinds, *Meranoplus bicolor* have communities of up to 10,000 workers. Their pace growth is medium, with the females measuring 8–9 mm and the males at 3–5 mm. Their body is red and abdomen is black.

Habitat: Species collected from grassy fields and ground.

Genus: *Formica*

Species: *Formica fusca* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Character

The size of *Formica fusca* ants, often known as typical black ants, is between 3 and 5 mm. The adult forms are glossy black or brown in hue. A broad head with poked antennae is characteristic of the black ant. The body features a narrow thorax that narrows into a small waist, which then joins the wide gut. The typical strength of black ant communities is between 4000-7000.

Habitat: Specimens gathered from bare ground and stony areas.

Figure 2: Species diversity documented from the study area i.e District Battagram.

DISCUSSION

This study, which lists 12 species of ants in 7 genera and 2 subfamilies, is the first account of ant diversity in the District of Battagram. Before Pakistan was even a country, Bingham (1903) conducted a thorough investigation into the variety of this significant group throughout the Indo-Pak subcontinent, Ceylon, and Burma. This was the first complete book on the ant fauna. Bingham (1903) found 498 varieties that were categorized into 79 genera. Due to Bingham's study, which spans the entire continent, including Ceylon and Burma, and encompasses nearly every kind of habitat, an enormous number of species were described during that period.

The present research focuses exclusively on one district in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, which lacks numerous areas in ant species. This may account for the 12 species found in 3 genera; however, Bingham (1903) included all of the kinds found in the present research in "Fauna of British India." Twelve species in all, most first identified within the research location, are identified in the present investigation. Twelve varieties of ants in all, divided into two subfamilies and seven genera: *Formicinae* and *Myrmicinae*, are both members of the *Formicidae* family.

Formicidae was determined to be the most prominent subfamily within that, with *Myrmicinae* coming in second. *Pheidole*, *Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, and *Monomorium* were the five genera that comprised the *Myrmicinae* subfamily. Additionally, two genera—*Camponotus* and *Formica*—are included in the *Formicidae*. *Camponotus*, which has five types, was found to be the most diverse genus if the distribution was examined at the genus scale. The other genera, *Formica*, *Crematogaster*, *Messor*, *Meranoplus*, and *Pheidole*, are each composed of a single species, except for *Monomorium*, which has two species. The *Camponotus* genus contains the species *C. copressus*, *C. castaneus*, *C. consobrinus*, *C. sericeus*, and *C. vagus*, which are cited in the current inquiry. Two species, *M. minimum* and *M. indicum*, were reported to be *Monomorium*, while the following genera only had one species each: *Crematogaster walshi*, *Formica fusca*, *Messor barbarus*, *Meranoplus bicolor*, and *Pheidole indica himalayana*.

The species *C. compressus*, *C. sericeus*, *M. indicum*, and *M. bicolor* are shared by the two investigations. Still, the present investigation carried out in District Battagram failed to find any of the genera reported by Shahid (2016), namely *C. muritanica*, *P. indica*, *P. binghami*, *T. simillimum*, *T. simithi*, *T. elatior*, *L. roberti coonoorensis*, *A. wroughtonii*, and *L. longitarsus*. According to these findings, District Attock has more ant diversity than District Battagram. It is possible to attribute the difference to variations in zoogeographical zones and environment. Attock has a wider biodiversity than Battagram because a greater variety of species of ant can thrive there thanks to its variety of sites.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have no financial or personal conflicts of interest for the publication of the current article.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, H.A., S. Noor, I.A. Sani, S. Kanwal, S. Khudaidad and M. Khawar. 2013. Ant fauna (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of Quetta, Balochistan, Pakistan. *Serranga*. 18(2): 47–59.
- Bingham, C.T. 1903. Hymenoptera. Vol. II: Ants and cuckoo-wasps. Taylor & Francis, London.
- Bodlah, I., R.M. Rasheed, A.G. Fareen, M.S. Ajmal and M.A. Bodlah. 2016. First record of two new species of genus *Tetraoponera* (Hymenoptera: Pseudomyrmecinae: Formicidae) from Pakistan. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*. 4(4): 1028–1030.
- Bolton, B. 1994. Identification guide to the ant genera of the world. Cambridge, Harvard University. 222 p.
- Bolton, B. and B. Bolton. 1995. A new general catalogue of the ants of the world. No. C/595.796 B6.
- Bolton, B., G. Alpert, P.S. Ward and P. Naskrecki. 2006. Bolton's catalogue of ants of the world: 1758–2005. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.
- Bolton, B. 1994. Identification guide to the ant genera of the world. Vol. null.
- Clarke, P.S. 1985. The natural history of sensitivity to jack jumper ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae *Myrmecia pilosula*) in Tasmania. *The Medical Journal of Australia*. 145(11–12): 564–566.
- Gottrup, F. and D. Leaper. 2004. Wound healing: Historical aspects. *EWMA Journal*. 4(2): 5.
- Haji, M. 2008. House ants of Karachi, Pakistan. Bachelor Thesis, Faculty of the Wilkes Honors College of Arts in Liberal Arts and Sciences, Harriet L. Wilkes Honors College of Florida Atlantic University, Jupiter, Florida. pp. 11.

- Haq, F., H. Ahmad, M. Alam, I. Ahmad and Rahatullah. 2010. Species diversity of vascular plants of Nandiar Valley, western Himalaya, Pakistan. *Pak. J. Bot.* Special Issue (S.I. Ali Festschrift). 42: 213–229.
- Hölldobler, B. and E.O. Wilson. 1990. *The Ants*. Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.
- Huang, M.H. and D.E. Wheeler. 2011. Colony demographics of rare soldier-polymorphic worker caste systems in *Pheidole* ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Insectes Sociaux*. 58: 539–549.
- Hölldobler, B. and E.O. Wilson. 1990. *The ants*. Belknap Press, Cambridge. 732 p.
- Kalif, K.A.B., C.A. Ramos, P. Moutinho and S.A.O. Malcher. 2001. The effect of logging on the ground-foraging ant community in Eastern Amazonia. *Studies on Neotropical Fauna and Environment*. 36: 215–219.
- Hölldobler, B. and E.O. Wilson. 1990. *The ants*. Harvard University Press. pp. 746.
- Khan, T., S. Ahmad, A. Rehman, A. Latif, W. Kamal, M. Afzaal, ... and S. Ullah. 2019. Species distribution of ants (Formicidae: Hymenoptera) of District Swabi, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.
- Majer, J. 1985. Recolonization by ants of rehabilitated mineral sand mines on North Stradbroke Island, Queensland, with particular reference to seed removal. *Aust. J. Ecol.* 10: 31–48. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-9993.1985.tb00861.x>
- Muhammad, S. 2004. Resource Management Plan Allai Forests.
- Shah, S.S.H., A. Khan, H. Ullah, A. Ullah, I. Khan, S. Ullah, ... and B. Ahmad. 2023. Biodiversity of order Coleoptera at selected localities of District Battagram through Malaise trapping system.
- Ullah, I., S. Ahmad, S.A. Mahmood, S.N. Khan, A. Khan and M. Yousaf. 2024. Faunistics and taxonomic study of spider (Arachnida: Araneae) fauna in District Battagram, KP, Pakistan. *Journal of Advance Zoology*. 45(S-4): 17–33.
- Ullah, A. and W. Khan. 2024. Feeding habits and diet composition of *Schizothorax plagiostomus* in Panjkora River, Malakand region, Pakistan. *Arxius de Miscel-lània Zoològica*. 22(1): 53–65.
- Umair, M. 2012. Taxonomic study of ants in Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Ph.D. dissertation / M.Sc. thesis, Department of Entomology, PMAS-Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan.
- Usman, K., S. Gul, H.U. Rehman, K. Pervaiz, H. Khan, S. Aslam, J. Hanif, S. Manzoor and T. Maqbool. 2017. Field observations on the incidence of ants fauna (Hymenoptera) of Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud.* 5(4): 390–393.
- Wetterer, J.K. 2017. Geographic distribution of the weaver ant *Oecophylla smaragdina*. *Asian Myrmecology*. 9: 2462–2362.
- Wilson, E.O. 1976b. Which are the most prevalent ant genera? *Stud. Entomology Worlds*. 19: 187–200.
- Wilson, E.O. and R.W. Taylor. 1967. *The ants of Polynesia* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Pacific Insects Monograph*. 14.
- Wilson, E.O. 1971. *The Insect Societies*. Harvard University Press.